

Memorandum

To: The Clerk to the Committee
Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs Office of Parliament
Osu-Accra

From: [REDACTED]
Communications Officer Humanists Association of Ghana & Mental Health Advocate.

Date: 30th September 2021

Re: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021 _____

Introduction

I am grateful to Parliament for the invitation and opportunity for members of the general public to submit their memorandum to assist the Committee in its review and consideration of the Proposed Bill.

I am Justice Okai-Allotey, a concerned citizen of Ghana and the Communications Officer and Member of the Humanist Association of Ghana. I found it prudent to write this memorandum to the Committee stating my displeasure on how inhumane the proposed bill is to every Ghanaian, including those who would primarily be affected should it be passed.

Background

"Humanism is a democratic and ethical life stance that affirms that human beings have the right and responsibility to give meaning and shape to their own lives. Humanism stands for the building of a more humane society through ethics based on human and other natural values in a spirit of reason and free inquiry through human capabilities. Humanism is not theistic, and it does not accept supernatural views of reality" - The Minimum Statement on Humanism, Humanists International. Ghana is a country of diverse people and cultures, which includes humanists and freethinkers like myself. I shared the mini-statement above to give proper perspectives on why as a country, we should separate religion from the state.

The Bill Contradicts the 1992 Constitution of Ghana

This bill is not only inhumane but violates several portions of our constitution, which I have cited below;

The 1992 Constitution of Ghana

- 1) guarantees the protection of the fundamental human rights of every person in Ghana, subject to the rights and freedoms of others and the public interest (Article 12);
- 2) guarantees the right to life of all persons (Article 13);
- 3) acknowledges the right to personal liberty (Article 14);
- 4) provides that the dignity of all persons shall be inviolable (Article 15);

5) provides that any person charged with a criminal offence shall be given a fair hearing within a reasonable time by a court (Article 19)

6) highlights the freedom of association (Article 21)

Clauses 20 of the proposed bill says any person arrested on charges stipulated in the bill and recants would undergo an approved medical treatment (Conversion Therapy). This provision goes contrary to the call by UN expert Victor Madrigal-Borloz, the Independent Expert on protection against violence and discrimination based on sexual orientation and gender identity. A statement released in Geneva on 8 July 2020 states the following "Practices known as "conversion therapy" inflict severe pain and suffering on lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans and gender-diverse (LGBT) persons, often resulting in long-lasting psychological and physical damage, a UN expert told the Human Rights Council while calling for a global ban." You can find the link to the said article here: (<https://www.ohchr.org/en/NewsEvents/Pages/DisplayNews.aspx?NewsID=26051&LangID=E>) this was also captured in the report of the expert to the UN General Assembly's Human Rights Council at their Forty-fourth session on 15 June –3 July 2020, with the link here: (<https://undocs.org/A/HRC/44/53>). United Nations OHCHR report, 2020 found that mandatory or coercive surgery on intersex individuals cause harm and violates the right to freedom from torture, ill-treatment and violence. (<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/26410397.2020.1731298>). No human being deserves to go through such inhumane treatments, and these clauses captured in this bill will harm marginalised Ghanaians.

Ghana has signed and ratified the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights which states in Article 2 the following; "Every individual shall be entitled to the enjoyment of the rights and freedoms recognised and guaranteed in the present Charter without distinction of any kind such as race, ethnic group, colour, sex, language, religion, political or any other opinion, national and social origin, fortune, birth or any status". This proposed bill essentially curtails the right of Ghanaians to assembly, free speech and joining any organisation of their choice. The bill further criminalises advocacy for upholding the rights of these sexual minority groups, which is a clear affront to our 1992 constitution. If allowed to be passed, this bill is going to have far-reaching consequences on the rights and freedoms of a lot of Ghanaians. Ghana is a secular country with a religious majority. It bestows us the opportunity to protect minority groups which is the opposite of what this bill seeks to do.

Conclusion

In conclusion, I recommend that this proposed bill gets rejected as it does not accord with Ghana's democratic values of freedom and justice for all its citizens.

1. <https://www.ohchr.org/en/NewsEvents/Pages/DisplayNews.aspx?NewsID=26051&LangID=E>

2. <https://undocs.org/A/HRC/44/53>

3. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/26410397.2020.173129>